

Collaborative mapping: San Antonio de Padua school, Tamesis municipality, Colombia

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scienti.minciencias.gov.co/cvlac/visualizador/generarCurriculoCv.do?cod_rh=0001991624

Carlos Enrique Santacruz Caicedo, Carlos Mario Velásquez Ramírez, Elis Enrique Kerguelen Cogollo. San Antonio de Padua Elementary School.

This abstract aims to present the results of a collaborative initiative for mapping ecological and tourism hotspots in Tamesis¹. This project came to life thanks to interinstitutional cooperation between the Digital University of the Institution of Antioquia, San Antonio de Padua Elementary School, and ESRI.

Digital University Institution of Antioquia's vision is to become a national and international leader and benchmark in inclusive higher education, with a territorial approach and a human-centered perspective, through our Next Digitality model. Guided by this vision, DigitalUI is committed to social development by partnering with elementary, secondary, vocational, and higher education institutions, as well as with local organizations and private entities. The goal is to offer an innovative and inclusive alternative for both students and their communities².

According to this vision, *ArcGIS for Schools* (Conceived by ESRI) and Territorial Nodes for Peace and Citizenship's DigitalUI³ generate an ecosystem of academic

cooperation through strategies such as collaborative tourism and environmental hotspot mapping initiatives.

Towards its implementation, a DigitalUI tenured professor⁴ and San Antonio de Padua elementary school teachers⁵ develop a mapping workflow based on investigation needs. This approach highlights that the municipality of Tamesis is considered one of the most hydrologically rich areas of the Antioquia Department in Colombia, with significant environmental and historical potential, as well as challenges across several ecosystem zones.

Identifying the main Tamesis basins, with the participation of the San Antonio de Padua Elementary School, the San Antonio basin river was selected as the initial study area.

The methodological steps of the mentioned workflow are as follows:

1. Instructional activities for elementary school teachers on ESRI licensing and usage through online meetings.

¹ Municipality in Antioquia, Colombia

² (Digital University Institution of Antioquia, 2025)

³ (Digital University Institution of Antioquia, 2025)

⁴ Sharon Angelica Sanchez Muñoz, tenured professor in Cadastral and Surveying

Technology at DigitalUI, specializing in GIS diagramming and technical support.

⁵ Carlos Enrique Santacruz Caicedo, Carlos Mario Velásquez Ramírez, Elis Enrique Kerguelen Cogollo. Teachers at San Antonio de Padua Elementary school, field mapping contributors.

Figure 1. Online instructional meeting.

2. Working sessions with teachers to design a data capture form using Survey123 based on the investigation needs.

Figure 2. Survey 123 form

3. GIS training sessions with students called “Learn mapping” are divided into three sessions:
 - a. Introduction to GIS
 - b. ArcGIS Online
 - c. Survey123: How does it work on my phone?

Figure 3. Students' online training session.

4. Field data capture: Elementary School teachers and students populated the Survey123 form with points related to tourism and environmental hotspots in the San

Antonio water basin.

Figure 4. Field work session

Figure 5. Point data collection.

5. Data processing and publishing: The Data point collected was carefully analyzed and processed to build a Storymap on ArcGIS Online.

Figure 6. Storymap Thumbnail available on <https://arcg.is/1GTLX43>.

Currently, these two institutions continue collecting and processing data to extend the project to other river basins within the municipality of Tamesis.

As part of this process, field mapping contributors at San Antonio Elementary School had the opportunity to adopt new

GIS tools, including Survey123 and ArcGIS Online.

This initiative benefits the communities of Tamesis by considering their eco-tourism potential and associated environmental risks, thereby supporting informed decision-making for the responsible protection and management of the San Antonio River basin.

In closing, intellectual property rights to the data and information generated through this project are shared equally by both institutions.